

A Spectrophotometric Study of Iron (III) *p*-Cresotic acid Chelate

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Spectrophotometric investigations indicate the formation of 1:1 chelate between iron (III) and *p*-cresotic acid. The stability constant of the chelate calculated from continuous variation and slope ratio method corresponded to 5.19 (log *k*) at pH 2.90.

Cresotic acids are well known to form complexes with inorganic ions¹⁻⁴. During the course of investigations associated with the development of a method⁵ for the estimation of iron (III) titrimetrically against EDTA in presence of aluminium, using *p*-cresotic acid as chelatometric indicator, the necessity of the knowledge of the stability constant became apparent. In previous communications⁶⁻⁸ from this laboratory we have reported our results on ortho and *m*-cresotic acid complexes. The present paper reports the investigations on the nature and composition of iron (III)-*p*-cresotate chelate.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-cresotic acid employed was a several times recrystallized product of B.D.H. (L.R.) quality. The recrystallizations were made from ethanol. Its solution was prepared as sodium salt.

Ferric ammonium sulfate used for preparing stock solution of iron (III) was an E. Merck Guaranteed reagent.

Sodium acetate and hydrochloric acid used for preparing buffers were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade.

Beckman DU spectrophotometer fitted with a dual thermospacer set for the maintenance of temperature in the cell compartment was used for absorbance measurements. The temperature was maintained at $35.5 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with the aid of an externally operated Hopler's ultra-thermostat. Corex cells of 10 mm width were used. All pH measurements were made with a Cambridge bench pattern pH meter.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The violet coloured iron (III)-*p*-cresotate chelate showed an absorption maximum at 560 $m\mu$ at varying iron (III) to ligand ratios in aqueous solutions. Beer's law was found to be applicable. The extinction coefficient (ϵ) corresponded to 1.88×10^3 at *pH* 2.90. Although λ_{max} was independent of *pH*, ϵ was markedly dependent on it. The optimal *pH* range for the formation of chelate was between 2.00–4.0.

The molar composition of the chelate was determined by Job's method as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper⁹. For this the absorbance of solutions prepared by mixing x ml. of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ sodium *p*-cresotate with $(10-x)$ ml. of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ iron (III) solution (where x was varied from 1 to 10 ml. and total volume was kept 25 ml.), were measured in different buffers of *pH* 1.93, 2.90 and 3.92. The data obtained are shown in Fig. 1 which gives the

Fig. 1. Continuous variation curves at different *pH* (curve 1 *pH* = 1.93; curve 2 *pH* = 2.90; curve 3 *pH* = 3.92.)

variation of absorbance with mole fraction of iron (III). Here curves 1, 2 and 3 refer to *pH* 1.93, 2.90 and 3.92 respectively. It may be seen from this figure that all the curves exhibit a maximum when the molar ratio of iron (III) to *p*-cresotate is 1 : 1. The formation constant of the chelate was calculated by the following formula

$$k = \frac{x(k_a + [\text{H}^+])}{k_a(a-x)(b-x)}$$

where x is the concentration of the complex at the equilibrium, a and b the initial concentrations of iron (III) and *p*-cresotic acid respectively, and k_a is the ionization constant of the

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acid. The values of k , classical stability constant are summarized in Table 1. The last column of Table 1 reports the values of thermodynamic stability constants obtained from the modified Debye Hückel equation.

TABLE 1

pH	Ionic strength	Classical stability constant $\log k$	Thermodynamic stability constant $\log k$
1.93	0.23	5.84	6.85
2.90	0.20	5.19	6.17
3.92	0.21	3.97	4.93

The standard free energy change, ΔF° , for the formation of the complex at 35.5° and pH 2.90 corresponded to -8.71 Kcal.

The stoichiometry of the complex was verified by the slope ratio method,¹⁰ which also indicated the formation of 1 : 1 chelate.

Similar to iron (III)—salicylate chelate, the structure of iron (III)—*p*-cresotate chelate may be represented as follows :

It will be of interest to compare the stability constant of iron (III)-*p*-cresotate chelate with iron (III) chelates of other substituted salicylic acids, which are given below :

Acid	Log k
Salicylic ¹¹	17.40
5-sulphosalicylic ¹²	3.68
<i>o</i> -cresotic ⁶	4.15
<i>m</i> -cresotic ⁷	4.67

It may be seen that the introduction of SO₃H or CH₃ group in the benzene ring lowers the tendency for chelation.

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